

Examination of renal vessels by doppler ultrasound to see renal & peri-renal vascular features in patients with or without renal disease

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Abstract:

Introduction: cases of renal failure increases all around the world (800 million in 2022 & 850 million in 2023), and therefore, it's necessary to find an examinational mode for early diagnosis of renal perfusion defect even if small and locally presented.

Aim of work: To visualize intra-renal, peri renal, and collateral vessels and to see the differences between vessels of all participants

Materials and Methods: an observational, random study to see intra-renal, peri-renal and collateral vessels, examining them by 2-dimensional, color flow, power doppler and spectral doppler. Number of cases (n=676; male 253, & female 423) from infant to old age, for diseased and healthy persons. All information are entered into Microsoft.

Results: all participants have the following atherosclerotic signs; beaded, interruption, amputation, and (n=676; 100%) also have one renal area or two areas without interlobar vessels that could be detected by color flow and (n=8; 1,18%) of them have one third of renal without visible interlobar vessels by power doppler mode, and (n=668; 98,82%) of them haven't visible arcuate arteries by both modes, thus, I was trying to apply another way of interpretation as a frequent sequencing of slow motion speed with screen recording by using of game phone which reveals vessels with multiple layers and colors in collateral circulation. While by, spectral doppler there are two signs; a progressive decrease in systolic/diastolic ratio from segmental to end of interlobar vessels and flattened diastolic velocity at cortical areas.

Conclusion: 1- Color flow mode constitute accurate, faster and simple examination to discover latent vascular change and perfusion defect even in small area of renal tissues that prompt an early medical intervention before the appearance of untreated lesion and it helps in taking prophylaxis against ischemic nephropathy. 2- applying of sequencing and frequent motion speed with screen recording enables the visualization of atherosclerosis of collateral vessels and the slowest black, White and gray vascular. 3- hyperechogenic and anechogenic areas is an important areas of renal perfusion and must be differentiated from fibrosis and cyst respectively. 4- progressive decrease in systolic/diastolic ratio and flat diastolic waves are an early signs of spectral doppler for diagnosis of intra-renal vascular atherosclerosis and cortical perfusion deficit.

Keywords: color flow, doppler, stenosis of renal arteries & veins, collateral vessels.

الكشف عن الأوعية الكلوية بدوبلر الموجات فوق الصوتية لرؤية مميزات الأوعية الكلوية وحول الكلوية في مرضى الكلى وغيرهم⁽¹⁾

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طبيب عام|| مستشفى النصر العام|| عيادة الأشول للأمراض الطبية والقلبية|| مدينة الضالع|| الجمهورية اليمنية

الإيميل: nashwansaleh49@gmail.com || أوركيد: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-1470-0943> || موبايل: 00967771601519**المستخلص:**

المقدمة: تزايد حالات الفشل الكلوي على مستوى العالم حيث بلغت في عام 2022 (800 مليون حالة)، بينما بلغت في عام 2023 (850 حالة)، مما يتطلب ضرورة الكشف المبكر عن نقص التروية الدموية الكلوية وبالأنخص الموضوعية منها، هدف البحث إلى رؤية الأوعية الدموية الكلوية وحول الكلوية المساعدة أو الإنقاذية، ورؤية العلامات الظاهرة في الأوعية الدموية المشخصة لتصلب الشرايين وتمثلت الأداة في دراسة ذات ملاحظة عشوائية لرؤية الأوعية الدموية الكلوية وحول الكلوية والمساعدة باستخدام جهاز الدوبلر الطيفي والطاقة واللوني، عدد الحالات (676) من الرضع وحتى كبار السن، أصحاء ومرضى، وتم إدخال المعلومات والنتائج في برنامج الميكروسوفت الحاسوبي، وبينت النتائج: بواسطة التدفق اللوني تم رؤية علامات التصلب الوعائي: السبحية، التقطع والبتر، ورؤية مناطق كلوية موضعية بدون أوعية دموية قوسية وبين الفصية في كل المرضى والأصحاء (عدد 676: 100%)، بينما هنالك (عدد 8: 1.18%) لم يتم رؤية أوعية دموية بين الفصية وقوسية وحول كلوية إنقاذية في النصف إلى ثلثي الكلية بالتدفق اللوني ودوبلر الطاقة، وعدد(668: 98.82%) لم يتم رؤية الشرايين القوسية لديهم بطريقتي التدفق اللوني ودوبلر الطاقة مع تفاوت مساحة الأوعية الدموية حول الكلوية أو المساعدة، وتم تجربة طريقة المشاهدة التسلسلية المتتابعة للبطينة للأوعية الدموية مع تسجيل الشاشة باستخدام جوال الألعاب لرؤية الألوان المتعددة والمختلفة الطبقات للأوعية الدموية الإنقاذية المساعدة. إما باستخدام الدوبلر الطيفي فهناك علامتان: هما نقصان تصاعدي للنسبة الإنقباضية الإنبساطية للشرايين الجزئية وبين الفصية، وتسطح الموجات الانبساطية في مناطق القشرة

الاستنتاج:1- التدفق اللوني طريقة كشف سهلة، سريعة وأكيدة وغير مكلفة للكشف المبكر عن التغيرات الوعائية الكامنة والخلل الوعائي ولو كان في منطقة صغيرة جدا. 2- مشاهدة الأوعية الدموية الكلوية بصورة متتابعة ومتكررة بالسرعة البطينة مع استخدام تسجيل الشاشة للجوال المستخدم للألعاب يمكننا من رؤية التغيرات التصلبية للأوعية الإنقاذية حول الكلوية والأوعية النسيجية الكلوية ذات اللون الأبيض أو الرمادي أو الأسود-3- المناطق البيضاء أو السوداء قد تكون مناطق وعائية هامة لتغذية الكلية لذلك يجب تفرقتها عن المناطق المتليفة أو الكيسية على التوالي-4- النقصان التصاعدي في النسبة الإنقباضية الإنبساطية والموجات الانبساطية المسطحة يشكلان علامتان خاصتان بالدوبلر الطيفي لتشخيص التصلب الوعائي ونقص التروية الدموية على منطقة القشرة

الكلمات المفتاحية: التدفق اللوني، الدوبلر، تضيق الشرايين والأوردة الكلوية، الأوعية الإنقاذية

INTRODUCTION.

Renal failure with atrophy become a disaster all around the globe, and as its cases are in increasing; (as said by Kovesdy C. P. 2022), in 2022 amounting to >800 million individuals^[1], & in 2023 amounting to 850 million individuals (as said by Bello AK. Et al. 2023)^[2], the searching for medical examination tool that will able to discover vascular renal problem before the renal failure become apparent.

herefore using of ultrasound color flow, power and spectral doppler modes are beneficial to this study for early diagnosis of renovascular problem in the latent stage as it is in the apparent one, as each one of these modes consummated each other, and using of modern game phone also helps in interpretation of vascular problems particularly if the color flow box opened completely.

Applying an oblique-lateral window in lateral decubitus for imaging of segmental, interlobar, arcuate and even most length of main renal arteries and veins, in addition to renal tissues perfusion, considered as a feasible and easiest way of examination to avoid intestinal gasses, obesity and abdominal distension in order to get visualization of all vessels of renal, peri-renal and collateral in both long and short axes.

Even with presence of doppler and contrast enhanced ultrasound or computed tomogram (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) Angiography, the problem that represented by presence of hypertension and renal failure with or without symmetrical or asymmetrical renal atrophy is stilling in increasing numbers yearly, and most of these patients was presented with pain; chronic recurrent renal pain, or with mild lower limbs edema, early morning eyelids edema, hypotension or hypertension and given symptomatic treatment with no looking for the possibility of lymphatic vessels or vascular blood problems, therefore, in my study I focused on the looking for signs of vascular inflammatory atherosclerosis by examining the possibility of color flow ultrasound to discover the vascular problem and tissue perfusion impairment in compare with

spectral and power doppler modes, a study that results in very important discovery for diagnosis of this problem not only in renal vessels and tissues but also in all other organs.

METHODS AND MATERIALS.

An observational random study, it performed at Dr. Nashwan Al-Ashwal Clinic for Medical and Cardiac Diseases, in Adhale governorate, Yemen Republic in the period from 12.06.2022 to 30.06. 2023. Participants that enrolled in the study are (n = 676); from them (n=423) 62,57 % are female, and (n=253) 37,4 % are male, ages were from 1-12 months (8 infants), and the others from 5 to 70 yrs. Old, as shown in table 1. Most of them (n=437; 64,65%) have many complaints, and (n=136; 20,11%) have gastric complaint where the others (n=103; 15,24%) haven't any complaint at the time of examination. Thus, I divided them into two groups; control (no complaints) and patients (the others).

The study was performed for two goals: the first is to see the renal blood vessels; arteries and veins, and collateral vessels by Ultrasonographic examination; renal or urogenital category, with using of a curved probe that has multi-frequency of 2 to 5 MHz, started with B-mode, then color flow, power and spectral doppler modes, applied routine examination method; preferred an oblique-lateral window in lateral decubitus, with some modification as Probe angulation and tilting to the degree that allowed to visualize complete renal shape and vascular tree and almost most of the para renal and collateral vessels. The second is to see the differences between vessels of all participants; as features of their renal vessels; by comparing between them in relation to vascular shapes, numbers and lengths, beside the presence or absence of blood flow (color flow) in renal areas and the extension of collateral vessels.

Table (1) represents number, sex and age of prticipants in the study

Sex of patients	Ages and numbers of patients					Total
	1–9 months	=>5years	>13 years	30-58 years	=>60 years	
Male	4	6	13	165	65	253
Female	4	3	38	278	100	423
Total	8	9	51	443	165	676

RESULTS:

All participants have the following atherosclerotic signs; beaded; multiple stenotic and dilated areas in the same artery, interruption; complete stenosis with bypass collateral segment connected between interrupted parts, amputation; complete stenosis with absence of post stenotic part, (n=676; 100%) and also they have either one renal area or two areas without interlobar vessels that could be detected by color flow, and (n=8; 1,18%) of them have one third of renal area without visible interlobar vessels by power doppler mode, and (n=668; 98,82%) of them haven't a visible arcuate arteries by both modes, as shown in the related figures.

By color flow and power doppler mode; Results of imaging of renal vessels are revealing the following features:

A) Renal vessels in all participating persons have many characteristics such as:

1- loss of arcuate arteries in children and young participants:

figure (1): 1st with color flow mode of lateral window; upper and lower poles without apparent arteries and lower pole is thinner than the upper one, with beaded and wider arteries in the upper-middle area (red arrows) and narrower beaded vessel in lower-middle area (green arrows), the main renal artery and vein also have beaded shapes. 2nd power doppler mode in infant; interlobar arteries in lower mid to pole smaller and narrower than upper part with collateral vessels in three aspects are apparent while the lateral one has only few points of vessels. 3rd color flow mode in lateral window; reveals lower pole atrophy (red arrow) and near to it a dark area is seen (yellow arrow), with one artery (red) near to it and two faint arcuate arteries above it (blue arrows), other arteries only basal parts are visible.

2- loss of arcuate arteries in adult and children:

figure (2): 1st photo reveals broken arcuate artery (blue arrow), 2nd photo the same photo in lateral view with directing the beam more anteriorly, to see part of main renal artery. 3rd photo reveals collateral vessels and parts of interlobar arteries in lateral aspect, with no arcuate arteries.

3- beading shapes due to multiple narrowing of inter-lobar arteries and visible parts of main renal arteries

figure (3): 1st photo shows more vessels in upper pole with one artery that is narrower than the others (red thicker arrow) and all of them are beaded (blue arrow), arteries are interrupted (red thin arrows), and the lower pole seen without interlobar arteries; only a few smaller red arteries were seen with thinner pole than the other, the blue vessels are veins, multiple beaded arteries near to the hilum. 2nd photo renal with thinner pole than the other, in upper pole there are three arteries; amputated (bigger red arrow), interrupted (thinner red arrow), lower pole thinner than upper with red, blue, and gray (gray arrow) color vessels, below to the hilum there are multiple beaded vessels (red and blue colors). 3rd is power doppler posterior view; reveals main renal artery with tortuous line and beaded with parts of bend end, upper renal artery end

connected to narrower arterial part of lower part segmental branch (blue arrow) that branched to multiple arteries one of them is interrupted (yellow arrow), other segmental branch in the upper lobe with lower and separated end (green arrow).

4- amputation-like shapes of one to many inter-lobar arteries as seen by color flow.

figure (4): 1st and 2nd photos show the same renal vessels by color flow and power doppler modes respectively show the difference between number, caliber & length of vessels by the two modes, in addition to make vessels that appeared amputated by color flow more visible by power doppler (red arrows), 3rd photo shows amputated upper renal pole artery (red arrow) and renal main artery completely beaded, interrupted with collateral vessels (blue arrow), and it shows that red and blue arterial segments according to the direction of blood flowing.

5- amputation-like shape of visible main renal arteries at different levels.

figure (5): 1st photo shows collateral vessels, interrupted renal artery with blue color with amputated branches and two red branches. 2nd photo shows red segment of renal artery connected to blue collateral renal artery that connected to collateral vessels (its blue because the flow is reversed then directed from the blue to the red one). 3rd photo shows the same of 2nd one with more extension of large vessels.

6- intra renal and extra renal collateral vessels to add the needed amount of blood supply to renal tissues

figure (6) 1st and 2nd photos compare between collateral vessels by color flow of two persons show red color connected to blue color vessel (red arrows), stenosis of interlobar artery (yellow arrow), amputated branch (blue arrow), stenosis of main renal vein with beaded shape (green arrow), and 3rd photo shows blue segment connected to two red artery parts (red arrows).

- 7- **by color flow some vessels are not seen completely either in the poles or in middle part** but they are seeing by power doppler mode, and in some patients more collateral vessels only seen by power doppler beside the inter lobar vessel and some renal inter lobar branches are seeing by color flow mode more than by power doppler.

figure (7): color flow and power doppler views are in the three photos and the 1stphoto lateral part reveals red and blue vessels in middle and in lower pole there are six like vessels with white color (red arrows) and the pole is thinner than upper one, a difference between the two photoes is presence of more collateral vessels in power doppler but interlobar vessels is more narrower distally in power doppler than in color flow (blue arrows), in 2nd photo 1st is by power doppler and beside it the color flow in which the interlobar and collateral vessels are more in the 1st. 3rd photo; orange and yellow color by power doppler and the other with blue color and part of it with red color it reveals two parts of segmental renal arteries (red arrows), four interlobar arteries (blue arrows), collateral vessels (green arrow), in color flow less vessels size, and numbers & dots of collateral vessels.

- 8- **peri renal arterial networks of smaller to larger and diffuse extension in childhood**

figure (8): 1st photo; multiple color network in 8 month children, one stage of collateral supply with gray color in second photo of same child, large extension of collateral vessels in 3 month children with area that has gray color vessels (red arrow), and stenotic collateral vessel (green arrow).

- 9- **renal blood supply via peri-renal networks of collateral circulation** as main source of blood flow due to great blood insufficiency via connection with one inter lobar renal artery then through it to other inter lobar arteries.

figure (9): 1stfrom left photo; 4 interlobar vessels with different colors and small collateral vessels near to lower pole, same photo 2nd part beside it, shows elongation of three vessels (red arrow two heads), and remaining of one vessel without elongation (blue arrows), with connection between them and the collateral vessels that enlarged more (green arrow). 2nd photo with two renal of same person shows blood supply from lateral border and connection between blue and red vessel, second part shows part of tree shape of renal vessels. 3rd photo shows blue and red segments of blood vessels located in three

areas of peri-renal region, with blue segment that connected between collateral vessels and part of interlobar artery; that flowing from collateral to interlobar vessel, and in opposite aspect the renal artery is beaded and narrowed with irregularity due to the bypass segments.

10- decreasing in peri-renal arterial and venous networks with years.

Figure (10): 1st photo from left shows part without apparent collateral vessels in adult, 2nd photo of 8 months children shows color flow and power doppler with part of upper pole and middle without apparent color vessels, i.e. gray vessels (slowest blood flow) only seen.

11 – stenosis of main renal vein and its branches, with presence of peri-renal collateral veins

figure (11):1st photo of color flow; from left shows renal blood vessels irregular main renal vein with stenosis (red arrow), appearance of last part of main renal artery only (blue arrow). 2nd photo of power doppler of 1st photo; shows widening of vessels diameters, stenosis of main renal vein (red arrow) and no increase in length of main renal artery (blue arrow), 3rd photo shows beaded shapes of interlobar renal arteries and veins, and no clear shape of main renal vessels except for multiple vessels like elongated networks.

12- renal blood supply from small segment of interlobar vessel in central area into the vessel connected to a large vessel of right liver lobe into other interlobar parts and into hepatic and peri-renal collateral network vessels along the liver lobe into the collateral vessels of lower pole of the right renal that look like black lake area, it contains interlaced smallest vascular structures

Figure(12): four photos show collateral blood supply from liver vessel (orange arrow) to renal vessel, and the 2nd one reveals the collateral vessels in liver lobe; it has red color and sends vessels into renal middle part, the 3rd one; from left, increased its lightening to show the dark like lake in renal and perirenal region which make gray and black color network to

be apparent more, it's the slowest collateral blood flow vessels and connected with the colored collateral vessels (as pointed by red arrows).

13- blood vessels can be visualized in all directions through lateral window in lateral decubitus if slightly modified.

figure (13): renal arteries and veins are seen in all directions, with two thirds of main renal artery and vein, by lateral window and slightly modified direction to anterior for visualization of main vessels, as in 1st photo main renal vein and artery appear interrupted (red arrow), and by 2nd photo (power doppler) connection is visualized (blue arrow) for main renal vein but not for main artery.

figure (14): 1st photo shows renal arteries in all areas, and the medial part has faint red arteries (blue arrows), in 2nd photo arteries present in all directions with some smaller arteries are interrupted (yellow arrows)

B) Renal tissues also have prominent features explained as the following:-

1- no or decreased extension of color flow in lower or upper or mid lateral parts, but flowing color is visualized by power doppler mode

figure (15):: 1st photo power doppler & color flow modes respectively, both renal poles are seen with a decreased to absent blood vessels in addition to the cortical regions, 2nd photo shows one large renal vessel with collateral vessels in the other side, and the photo beside it shows the vascular amputation due to long vascular part occlusion (red arrows) with blood flow from separated collateral vessels.

2- detection a lot of colors by color flow that represents a multiple levels or layers of collateral vessels.

figure (16): 1st & 2nd photos; in infants, show multiple colors by color flow mode; visualized more clearly by using of a sequenced slow motion and screen recording of a modern phone, in the middle photo there are black, gray and white lines of vessels are also seen, and dark blue to black vessel (red arrow) connected to gray segment between it and the area of red collateral network (yellow arrow), and a white color network in peri-renal is extended to near the red network in other aspect (blue arrows), the last photo shows multiple colors of collateral vessels and longitudinal homogeneous colors that like artifact in adults (yellow arrows).

3- decreased width of renal size in upper or lower poles that causes a change in renal shape or in both of them that preserved near to normal shape before an apparent deterioration of renal function tests has become detected.

figure (17): an absent of blood vessels in both poles of renal in 1st and 3rd photos with atrophied lower pole of third one, in the 2nd photo; large vessels in upper pole with smallest vessels in mid and lower pole that was atrophied slightly, around the renal there is hyperchogenic floor like area (red arrow) and black areas between it and the renal (blue arrows), and also gray vessels like in between it and the renal (green arrows).

figure (18): left renal was atrophied, and upper pole of right renal is continuing its atrophy over the old atrophying of whole renal, there is hyper echogenic tissues in the upper pole and at the middle there is cyst like with hyper echogenic irregular rim and extended threads into the cyst like area as white lines or vessels like.

C- Patients with hypotension have larger areas of extension of peri-renal arterial and venous networks while the patients with hypertension have a smaller one.

figure (19): 1st photo shows collateral vessels by color flow mode in hypotensive persons, 2nd one shows decreased collateral vessels and smaller amputated vessels by color flow mode, 3rd photo shows decreased to absent interlobar vessels and smaller collateral vessels by color flow and wider extension of collateral vessels by power doppler mode in patients with moderate hypertension.

D- Presence of renal hyper echogenic and anechogenic areas.

figure (20): renal blood vessels smaller, amputated, stenosed and obliterated with presence of four colors in collateral vessels, white (red arrow), red brown (blue arrow), dark blue (yellow arrow), gray (green arrows), white vessels (gray arrows), 2nd photo shows renal cyst (red arrow), black vessels (blue arrow), gray vessels (green arrows), white vessels (gray arrows), other collateral vessels red, orange, brown and blue are clearly visible.

II- By spectral doppler: this mode reveals the following:

1- progressive decrease in systolic/diastolic ratio from hilum to cortex

figure (21): 1st photo shows main renal vein (blue arrow) and arterial blood flow waves (red arrow), which are higher;(80.0cm/s systolic velocity & 29.5 cm/s diastolic; = 2,7%), than the 2nd photo that shows interlobar blood flow waves (red arrow) with (systolic velocity 32.7cm/s & diastolic velocity 12.3 cm/s; 2,65%), and last photo shows lowest blood flow waves; (systolic velocity 13.4 cm/s) & diastolic velocity 7.5 cm/s; = 1,78%), of distal interlobar artery (red head arrow), there

is a difference between them other than the progressive decrease in systolic diastolic ratio which is the flattening of diastolic waves of middle and cortical areas (yellow arrows).

2- increase in systolic/diastolic ratio at mid-level followed by flattening of diastolic velocity:

figure (22): 1st photo shows two blood flow waves of ;due to respiration, with flattening of diastolic velocity in one wave (red arrow) and oblique descent in others (blue arrows); (recorded blood flow in two neighboring arteries), and the 2nd photo shows a decrease in systolic/diastolic ratio with flattening of diastolic waves velocity.

3- flattening of diastolic velocity with a decrease in systolic velocities that be more prominent at cortical level.

figure (23): 1st photo shows flattened and no decrease in height of diastolic velocities (13.1 cm/s) while systolic velocity is 23.1 cm/s, and ratio is 1,76% in pre distal of middle inter lobar artery near to upper pole, the 2nd photo shows more decrease in systolic velocity to 17.7 cm/s and decrease in diastolic velocity to 8.6 cm/s with ratio of 2,06% in pre distal of middle interlobar artery near to lower pole that enriched with collateral vessels; and the systolic/diastolic ratio not represent the diastolic velocities in the same artery but represents a difference in arterial walls stiffness of different poles in the same renal.

4- dilated segment in pre stenotic has highest velocity while the post stenotic segment not dilated and has the lowest velocity

figure (24): velocity in pre stenotic and post stenotic segments respectively; the first has 33.8 cm/s peak systolic velocity and 12.3 cm/s peak diastolic velocity while the post stenotic segment has 17.7 cm/s peak systolic velocity and 7.0 cm/s diastolic velocity.

figure (25): same patient with color flow photos the 1st shows interlobar arteries in a phase of diastolic while the 2nd shows arteries in systolic phase; by difference of arterial fullness, first stenosis (red arrow), and second stenosis (blue arrow), while post stenotic segment (yellow arrows), also the veins are narrowed and dilated in pre stenotic segment (green arrows).

DISCUSSION.

Color flow and power doppler modes show renal vascular at any point in the renal and peri-renal areas, as seen in these photos by color flow mode the renal vessels; main renal, segmental and interlobar arteries, in addition to the veins, are visualized as shown in figures (13 & 14 1st photos), also show the arcuate arteries; as shown in figure (2; 1st and 2nd photos), and collateral vessels as shown in figures (6, 8, 9, 10, 12, 19 & 20).

Power doppler mode shows renal vascular; arteries & veins, as shown in figures (1; 2nd photo, 3; 2nd & 3rd photo, 4; 2nd photo, 5; 3rd photo, 7, 10; 4th photo, 11; 2nd & 3rd, 13; 2nd, 14 2nd photos, 15; 1st photo & 19; 5th photo), and make visualization of the vessels wider, and kinking of venous segments that not visualized by color flow become more apparent by power doppler as shown in figure (13).

By both modes the shape, length and extension of vessels can be detected, and beading (all figures of color flow and power doppler), kinking (11 & 13), amputation (5, 6, 7, 8 & 9) or absence of vascular segments (9, 12, 14, 15, 17, & 18) are feasibly and easily visualized as shown in related figures. Loss of part of renal perfusion is detected by absence of interlobar renal artery/arteries as shown in figures (9, 10, 11, 14, 15, 17), with areas that have not large blood vessels, or have smaller and narrower vascular branches as shown in figure (3, 4, 5, 7, and 9). In addition to these signs there are collateral vessels either between two parts of interlobar artery as blue segment due to the reverses blood flow from up to down as shown in figures (6 & 9) or between lower liver lobe vessel and right renal as shown in figure (12).

These collateral vessels start to decrease in their extension at early age like in 3 months of age and continuing in decrease with aging as shown in figures (8, 10, & 16), and it was decreasing more in patients with hypertension as seen in figure (19), it seen to be largely extended in patients with hypotension as seen in same figure, this give a clue; that large extension of collateral vessels helps to decrease systemic blood pressure while its smaller extension contributed to elevate the blood pressure (i.e. one cause of hypertension is atherosclerosis of vessels of collateral circulation also); this explains the involvement of collateral vessels by atherosclerotic process, and the renal areas without blood vessels if visualized frequently by sequencing motion of slow speed and screen recording by helps of modern game phone will lead to the appearance of another part of collateral circulation that visualized as white, gray and black vessels which represents the speed of blood flow in these vessels as shown in figures (8, 10 16 & 20) and there are two extreme of this; one is hyperechogenic as shown in figures (17 & 20) and the other is anechogenic like a cyst as shown in figure (12), that must be differentiated from fibrosis and cyst respectively using this mode of interpretation to see the vascular structures extended from these lesions or connected to it, exactly as the multiple color of color flow that must be differentiated by this mode from the artifacts as shown in figure (16).

By spectral doppler I was concentrating on the progressive decrease in systolic/diastolic ratio from hilum to cortex which also reveals flattening of diastolic velocity in distal areas toward the end of interlobar arteries and all renal borders as shown in figures (21, 22, & 23), which pointing to the early loss of arcuate arteries at infant age as shown in figures (1, 8, 10 & 16), which present as incomplete shape in patients that used drugs against autoimmune liver disease as shown in figures (1 & 2). Thus, these two signs; diastolic waves flattening at end of interlobar arteries and absence of arcuate arteries at early years of life are early signs to diagnose renovascular atherosclerosis and to follow up an improvement after therapy.

Many researchers used color flow doppler for semi-quantitative evaluation of intra-renal vascularization and detected 4 stages; stage 0 unidentifiable vessels to stage 3 that characterized by identification of renal vessels and arcuate arteries in all the renal field of view (as said by Barozzi L. et al. 2007)^[3], but they are not focused on the apparent structural changes of venous and arterial walls and lumens as beading (multiple stenosis and dilatation of segments between two stenosis along the vessels lengths), interruption (complete occlusion of vessel part but with presence of collateral bypass vessel between pre-stenotic and post stenotic vascular parts in same vessel), amputation (complete occlusion of vessel part and absence of post stenotic vascular part), and intra-renal or peri-renal collateral vessels, all of these changes will be benefiting to know if there is inflammatory atherosclerotic process or not, in order to predict about renal perfusion state particularly when associated with areas of very small vessels as shown in figures (11, 14, 15, 17), or with no vessels as shown in figures (5, 12, 15, 17, 18, 19 & 20), these changes due to atherosclerosis are already proven in the study of examination of whole lengths of coronary arteries by echocardiography^[4].

Other researchers, as (Kovesdy C. P. 2022)^[1], and (Schnell D. & Darmon M. 2012)^[5] were focused on color flow as a guide to put the spectral sample on a part of vessel to detect peak velocity of systolic, and resistive index^[1, 5] as parameters for diagnosis of renovascular stenosis, no one pointed to a progressive decrease in systolic/diastolic ratio from hilum to cortex as a sign of renovascular stenosis, as shown in figure (21), while the resistive index can be affected by intra-abdominal pressure as said by (Hurrler T. et al. 2010, Kirkpatrick A. W. et al. 2007, & Ball C. G. et al. 2006)^[6, 7, 8], it also affected by heart rate, mean arterial pressure, oxygen and carbon dioxide levels and age (as said by Bello AK. 2023)^[2], in addition to this the patient may unable to hold his breathing for a time that needed to put the sample on an arterial part and monitor the flowing; i.e. the sample place may be changed and measures another part of neighboring arteries. Also they were focusing on peak velocity of systolic flow of more than 200 cm/s, (as said by Chain S. et al 2006)^[9], for renal artery and not take into their account the presence of multiple stenosis for example; in one artery, as shown by beaded arterial walls, which of course will result in decreasing of peak systolic and diastolic velocities, and also other researcher had detected that the post stenotic dilatation is due to high speed of flowing and colliding with lumen walls of renal artery (as said by Park B. K.)^[10].

in post stenotic segment as he was pointing to it in figure 2, in his research^[10], but if one will be focusing his eye on the blue segment he will see multiple parts inserted or connected into the previous red segment and vice versa, thus the narrower part of the blue segment is adjacent to narrower part of red segment that formed a narrower vessel part; i.e. stenotic area, which leads to dilatation of pre stenotic vascular part,, and from it many collateral vessels are connecting into post stenotic segment wall; seen as irregular area, why the pre stenotic segment is dilated? because it exposed to high internal pressure from lumen to walls in order to push the blood via the stenosis and this pressure will result in walls weakness and bulging leads to lumen dilatation due to the continues bulging of walls of pre stenotic segments, as a result of elevated pressure to a level that permits flowing of blood via lumen of stenosis; as shown in figure(25), and figure (24), that show increased of velocity in pre stenotic and decreased in post stenotic segments. The rising pressure in pre stenotic segment leads to opening of collateral vessels to bypass the stenosis^[4].

Then with time the peak systolic velocity will be decreasing as a result of decompression by opening of collateral vessels from pre-stenotic segments to post-stenotic segments (as said by Al-Ashwal NSM 2022)^[4], and when the collateral vessels are increasing in numbers they are forming a network like arteries which will be increasing in a direct proportion to the extension of atherosclerosis; seen as wide area of color and contained an interlaced vessels as shown in the collateral vessels figures, then leads to a decrease in blood pressure level as a result of large networks formation from arteries and veins because the veins also affected by the inflammatory atherosclerotic process as shown in figure (11, 13, 16, 17, 19). Thus, this process caused two medical presentation; a hypertension and hypotension, depending on degree of systemic and collateral vascular atherosclerosis as shown in figures (4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 18, 19 & 20). Other researchers also were focusing on power doppler as a mode to see global renal perfusion and parenchymal microvasculature due to its greater sensitivity to flow and reduced of angle dependence (as said by Helenon, O. et al 1998)^[11].

But in my study I focused also on the difference between color flow and power doppler in visualization of all vessels, and it reveals the ability of power doppler to make the apparently unseen segment of large arteries by color flow visualized by power doppler as shown in figures (4, 7, 11, 13 & 14), beside this, it helps to visualize the vessels of slow blood flow as the collateral vessels as shown in figures (5, 19), but it failed to show the slowest blood flow vessels as shown in figure (10) a point that solved by color flow motion and a frequent sequencing of slow motion speed with screen recording by using a game phone, a step that elucidated another level of blood flow that is the slowest one as shown in figure (8 & 16), which characterized by appearance of multiple colored vessels arranged in layers and each one pointing to a particular speed till the appearance of white, black and gray colored vessels as shown in figures (17 & 20) which is the slowest one. This interpretation way will have been benefiting in detection if there is slowest blood flow into the atrophied renal or not, and if the echogenic area is a cyst or network of black vessels or if the hyper echogenic area is fibrosis or network of white and gray vessels respectively. Therefore, each one of these modes is complementing to each other, but the color flow in oblique-lateral window with lateral decubitus leads to faster, easiest and accurate diagnosis of the condition of renal perfusion and helps to make early decision before the progression of renal hypo-perfusion to a permanent defect.

Other ways for examination of renal perfusion and renal arteries include contrast enhanced ultrasonography, but it cannot used in every patient (as mentioned in Xu, Y. et al. research 2020)^[12], new technique of dynamic color doppler signal quantification, but this technique affected by movements and breathing artifacts (as said by Scholbach T, 2004)^[13], CT or MRI Angiography, also these technique may results in allergic reaction, decreased renal function, or serious complications due to iodine or gadolinium contrast material (as said by Gleeson, T. G. et al. 2004, Grobner, T. et al. 2007, & Grobner, T. 2006)^[14, 15, 16], where by using color flow doppler ultrasonography the lateral-oblique window can be used in everyone without any bad effects and without a need to hold breathing.

In spite of what said by (Park, B.K. 2022): that the color doppler of kidneys not an ideal approach for detecting renal artery stenosis, because the renal perfusion can be normal in early stage^[10], but because the intra-renal arterial and venous vessels which visualized clearly by color flow and their images can be magnified to take a measurements of the pre stenotic, stenotic and post stenotic areas; where the post stenotic area represents the normal vascular diameter area of intra-renal vessels or even the visible part of the main renal artery, and because the pre-stenotic segment may be reaching the dilatation point or not, then make the calculation to get the percentage of vascular area patency of the stenotic one, then to get the stenotic level, if there is one or two areas of stenosis but if there are multiple stenotic areas or the length of the vessel has string of beads, then even the spectral doppler will not give the true level of stenosis because the intravascular pressure either was decreasing as decompression by newly opening collateral vessels, or peak velocity not represents only the sampled area

but also the total beaded length of the sampled vessel, because the blood vessel isn't a fixed tubular structure but rather it has a living mechanism.

And other researchers; (Corradi, F., Via, G., & Tavazzi, G. 2019)^[17], said: that the interlobar renal arteries color flow only is benefiting in decided if there is normal perfusion, hypo perfusion or unperfused depending on the visualized vessels as found in figure 1, and also the same that mentioned in table 4 in a research by Park, B.K. 2022^[10], but these researchers not described the shape, number and vascular size, in spite of presence of vascular narrowing & dilatation, interruption & tapering, and not take into their consideration the whole length of intra-renal vessels, because they considered the color flow ultrasonography of renal vessels only as a guide to perform the spectral doppler velocities, where in my research I have explained the change in renal vascular shapes, presence or absence of intra-renal and collateral vessels, beside the multiple layers or levels and colors of collateral vessels into the renal.

Also the color flow of main renal, segmental, and intra-renal arterial and veins as it reveals a local picture of inflammatory disease that represented by beading, interruption and amputation of vascular branches, beside an involvement of collateral vessels pointing to presence of chronic persistent inflammatory process of vascular system with continuation of body rescuing mechanism; i.e. continuing formation of collateral vessels against continuous inflammatory progression, i.e. an involvement of defensive mechanism itself, therefore, it reflects also a systemic vascular involvement, as supported by involvement of coronary and cerebrovascular atherosclerosis in patients with renal arteries stenosis (Stratigis, et al 2018)^[18] and (Kawarada, O. et al 2007)^[19].

Beading of renal vascular system; main, segmental, interlobar & collateral vessels, results in renal tissues problem as in arterial blood supply and venous blood drainage, that leads to poor or temporarily renal venous stasis, which presented clinically as flank fullness with burning sensation and/or pain, and with eye puffiness or transient morning eyelids swelling, till the formation of new collateral vessels. Therefore, this sign of renal vascular disease (beading or string of beads) is in need to put it in a pathological category depending on similarities between it and ultrasonographic signs of known diseases, for example, string of beads in patients with fibromuscular dysplasia and in patients with atherosclerosis, where in the first the disease involved mid to distal renal artery (Niepen, P.V. et al)^[20], while in the second it reveals that string of beads also is presented in renal artery and mimicking fibromuscular dysplasia (Higashi, H. et al)^[21], this similarity in presence of different etiology and age of presentation needs to compare between them and patients in my study; where the presentation of fibromuscular dysplasia is in middle age, characterized by: in fist type; multifocal stenosis and dilatation in mid to distal renal artery, and in second type; focal one which may occur in any part of the artery, and also presence of other signs as aneurysms, dissections, and arterial tortuosity, but this disease is clinically silent, in spite of involvement of more than one vascular bed; i.e. multivessel fibromuscular dysplasia in 30% to 57% of patients (Niepen, P.V. et al 2021)^[20], while the atherosclerosis is detected in second decade of life and develop further with age, involved medium and large arteries, and recently it has potent risk factor which is the family history as a genetic component (Mota, R. et al. 2017)^[22],

The participating persons and patients in my study were from age 1 month to 60 years and more, all of them have "a string of beads" in intra-renal, segmental and two thirds of main renal vessels; even complete obliterations of the main renal artery and renal get supply from another areas; i.e. replacement of main renal artery by another one from another region, some of them have manifestation of disease and others haven't. Thus, presence of multiple signs of vascular disease, as "a string of beads"; multiple sequence of stenosis & dilatation, along with other signs; like tortuosity, tapering, interruption and amputation like segments in all of them even the infants, beside the presence of collateral vascular segments bypassing the stenosis and connecting pre-stenotic segment with post-stenotic segment or collateral vessels from distant area like the liver

or spleen or another neighboring organs that also involved from the age of infants; both in male and female, belonged to participating (healthy & diseased) persons in my study.

Hence, new discovering of genetic component in etiology of atherosclerosis (Mota, R. et al. 2017)^[22], make the risk factors like high fat intake and higher blood pressure in inquiry, because if these signs of vascular problem like stenosis and dilatation that present even in infants and in female and male either in those with hypertension, normal or hypotension are due to atherosclerotic process, then the pathological process that is responsible for development of atherosclerosis is the main responsible for attraction of fat and depositing it in vascular wall, which explains why the atherosclerotic lesion present even in patients with normal lipid profile, and in those that abstained of fatty foods, and will be increased the suspicion of atherosclerosis in any patient even the infant.

And if atherosclerosis is mimicking fibromuscular dysplasia as aforementioned, that main presence of stenosis and dilatation due to vascular wall hypertrophy with no plaque, or that both diseases could be presented in one patient as said by (Persu, A. et al 2021)^[23], then another provoking agent is responsible for these changes like a microorganism as bacterial or viral; for example, H. pylori is widely distributed in the world (Katelaris, P. et al 2021)^[24], and it is transmitted by milk and dairy products of commercial origin and of cow's milk (Mohammed, N.S. 2018)^[25], and by infected eggs, chicken, and meat, also by potatoes that irrigated during agricultural by sewerage or treated sewage water if eaten raw or boiled only by ordinary method, and if all of these; for example, milk and dairy products, with other types of foods are consummating by all persons in the world, and also all persons have hygienic behavior; used latrines and wash their hands after it, and before & after each meal, then these habits make no difference between peoples in developed and developing countries, particularly if all of them buy packaged foods and beverages.

Thus, in spite of personal hygiene, and of H. pylori infection treatment, the bacteria had established an inflammatory process within minutes of gastric entrance that remains and progressing in body even after achieving of H. Pylori eradication, and more activation is occurring to it after new ingestion of bacteria via the packaged foods, milk and beverages, (Al-Ashwal, N.S.M. 2020)^[26], as also it was activating by infection with COVID-19 and its consecutive variants, also both diseases are associated with cardiovascular disease (Aramouni, K. et al. 2023)^[27] & (Vilaplana-Carnerero, C. et al. 2023)^[28], an association that may continuing for decades, due to the continued circle of viral transmission between humans and animals and the persistent ingestion of H. Pylori via contaminated and infected foods, beverages and animals respectively. Therefore, vascular diseases and organs dysfunction will be increasing and accelerated in all persons even the infants, which leads to catastrophic health problem as an increasing in new cases of ordinary diseases and an aggravating of chronic one also. Thus, screening of blood vessels of patient organs by color flow ultrasonography will shorten the time needs to discover a changes in blood vessels of human organs, particularly, if these signs of vascular changes; like string of beads, tapering, tortuosity and others are also detected in patients and participants from all age groups in their whole lengths of coronary arteries; as I described them in previous study, and in renal vessels in recent study.

CONCLUSION.

- An Oblique-Lateral window in lateral decubitus helps to avoid abdominal gases and obesity, and visualization of whole lengths of segmental and inter lobar vessels.
- Signs of renal atherosclerosis as beading, interruption, amputation and absence of arcuate arteries are present early in infantile age of life and progressing with human aging; which necessarily, need a searching for the causative agent of inflammatory atherosclerotic process from an infant to old age.

- Collateral vessels in hypotensive patients are larger than in hypertensive and its atherosclerotic changes appear early in life (in infants) and continuing in progress.
- Color flow, power and spectral doppler modes of ultrasonography are helpful in diagnosing early vascular changes of atherosclerosis in renal arteries.
- Color flow mode constitute a valuable, faster and simple examination to discover latent vascular change and perfusion defect even in small area of renal tissues that prompt an early medical intervention before the appearance of untreated lesions.
- Applying of sequencing and frequent motion speed with screen recording enables the visualization of atherosclerosis of collateral vessels and the slowest black, White and gray vessels.
- Hyperechogenic and anechogenic areas may be the third and fourth systems of renal perfusion and must be differentiated from fibrosis and cyst respectively.
- progressive decrease in systolic/diastolic ratio and flat diastolic waves are an early signs of spectral doppler for diagnosis of intra-renal vascular atherosclerosis.

RECOMMENDATIONS.

1. This way of examination depends on direct visualization of intra renal, peri-renal and collateral vessels which be easiest than measuring of blood flow velocities that has some difficulties due to a need to hold breathing.
2. Applying this examination leads to early diagnosis of even small area in renal tissues with decreased blood vessel branches that reflects a decrease in renal perfusion, like also it was succeeded in discovering of atherosclerotic signs in whole lengths of coronary arteries in previous study.
3. This way of examination allows searching of renal perfusion in largest samples of population that leads to know the problem of renal vessels from intra-uterine fetal age to old one, beside another organs also, like it proven before.
4. Of course it permits a planning for an early prompt medical intervention which is better than a late one, if we need to decrease the cases of renal failure in the world and the associated vascular problems in other organs, because of the inflammatory atherosclerotic process that is widely extended in the human bodies and is a lifelong disease due to the persistence provoking of this process, therefore, it is worth a world consideration.
5. Therapeutic study is already performed in parallel with this study and will published Inshaa Allah in next time.
6. Large study may be done by a large researching center or by government centers.

COMPETING INTERESTS:

There are no competing interests.

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REFERENCES.

- [1] Kovesdy C. P., Epidemiology of chronic kidney disease: update (2022), *Kidney International Supplements* 2022; 12, 7-11: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.kisu.2021.11.003>

- [2] Bello AK, Okpechi IG, Levin A, Ye F, Saad S, Zaidi D, Houston G, Damster S, Arruebo S, Abu-Alfa A, Ashuntantang G, Caskey FJ, Cho Y, Coppo R, Davids R, Davison S, Gaipov A, Htay H, Jindal K, Lalji R, Madero M, Osman MA, Parekh R, See E, Shah DS, Sozio S, Suzuki Y, Tesar V, Tonelli M, Wainstein M, Wong M, Yeung E, Johnson DW. ISN-Global Kidney Health Atlas: A report by the international society of Nephrology: An assessment of global kidney health care status focusing on capacity, availability, accessibility, affordability and outcomes of kidney disease. International society of Nephrology, Brussels, Belgium.2023. www.theisn.org/global-atlas.
- [3] Barozzi L, Valentino M, Santoro A, Mancini E, Pavlica P. Renal ultrasonography in critically ill patients. Crit Care Med 2007; 35:S198-205, <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.CCM.0000260631.62219.B9>
- [4] Al-Ashwal NSM., Examination of whole lengths of coronary arteries by color flow echocardiography, AJSRP 2022; 6(6):30Dec2022, 49-70, <https://doi.org/10.26389/AJSRP.L070322>
- [5] Schnell D., Darmon M. Renal Doppler to assess renal perfusion in the critically ill: a reappraisal. Intensive Care Med 2012; 38: 1751-1760, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00134-012-2692-z>
- [6] Hurrler T, Tischer A, Meyer A, Feiler S, Guba M, Nowak S, Rentsch M, Bartenstein P, Hacker M, Jauch KW. The intrinsic renal compartment syndrome: new perspectives in kidney transplantation. Transplantation 2010; 89:40-46, <https://doi.org/10.1097/TP.0b013e3181c40aba>
- [7] Kirkpatrick AW, Colistro R, Laupland KB, Fox DL, Konkin DE, Kock V, Mayo JR, Nicolaou S, Renal arterial resistive index response to intraabdominal hypertension in a porcine model. Crit Care Med 2007; 35:207-213, <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.CCM.0000249824.48222.B7>
- [8] Ball CG, Kirkpatrick AW, Yilmaz S, Monroy M, Nicolaou S, Salazar A, Renal allograft compartment syndrome: an underappreciated postoperative complication. Am J Surg 2006; 191:619-624, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjsurg.2006.02.013>
- [9] Chain S, Luciarci H, Feldman G, Berman S, Herrera RN, Ochoa J, et al. Diagnostic role of new Doppler index assessment of renal artery stenosis. Cardiovascular ultrasound 2006; 25(4):4. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1476-7120-4-4>.
- [10] Park, B.K. Gray-scale, Color Doppler, Spectral Doppler, and Contrast-Enhanced Renal Artery Ultrasound: Imaging Techniques and Features. J. Clin. Med. 2022, 11, 3961. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm11143961>
- [11] Helenon O, Correas JM, Chabriaix J, Boyer JC, Melki P, Moreau JF. Renal vascular doppler imaging: clinical benefits of power mode. Radiographics, Nov-Dec;1998; 18(6):1441-54; discussion 1455-7. <https://doi.org/10.1148/radiographics.18.6.9821193>.
- [12] Xu, Y., Li, H., Wang, C., Zhang, M., Wang, Q., Xie, Y., Shao, X., Tian, L., Yuan, Y., Yan, W., et al. Improving prognostic and chronicity evaluation of chronic kidney disease with contrast enhanced ultrasound index-derived peak intensity. Ultrasound Med & Biol 2020; 46, 2945-2955. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultrasmedbio.2020.06.020>.
- [13] Scholbach T, Dimos I, Scholbach J. A new method of color doppler perfusion measurement via dynamic sonographic signal quantification in renal parenchyma, Nephron Physiol 2004;96:p99-104, <https://doi.org/10.1159/000077380>
- [14] Gleeson, T. G., Bulugahapitiya, S. Contrast induced nephropathy. Am. J. Roentgenol.2004;183, 1673-1689. <https://doi.org/10.2214/ajr.183.6.01831673>.
- [15] Grobner, T., Prischl, F.C. Gadolinium and nephrogenic systemic fibrosis. Kidney Int. 2007;72, 260-264. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.ki.5002338>
- [16] Grobner, T. Gadolinium-A specific trigger for the development of nephrogenic fibrosing dermopathy and nephrogenic systemic fibrosis? Nephrol. Dial. Transpl. 2006;21, 1104-1108. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ndt/gfk062>
- [17] Corradi, F., Via, G., Tavazzi, G. What's new in ultrasound based assessment of organ perfusion in the critically ill: expanding the bedside clinical monitoring window for hypoperfusion in shock, intensive Care Med. 2019; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00134-019-05791-y>
- [18] Stratigis, S.; Stylianou, K.; Kyriazi, P.P.; Dermitzaki, E.K.; Lygerou, D.; Syngelaki, P.; Stratakis, S.; Koukouraki, S.; Parthenakis, F.; Tsetis, D.; et al. Renal artery stenting for atherosclerotic renal artery stenosis identified in patients with coronary artery disease: Does captopril renal scintigraphy predict outcomes? J. Clin. Hypertens. 2018, 20, 373-381. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jch.13160>
- [19] Kawarada, O., Yokoi, Y., Morioka, N., Takemoto, K. Renal artery stenosis in cardio and cerebrovascular disease: Renal duplex ultrasonography as an initial screening examination. Circ. J. 2007;71, 1942-1947. <https://doi.org/10.1253/circj.71.1942>

- [20] Niepen, P.V., Robberechts, T., Devos, H., Tussenbroek, F., Januszewicz, A., Persu, A., Fibromuscular dysplasia: its various phenotypes in everyday practice in 2021. *Kardiol Pol.* **2021**; 79 (7-8): 733-744. <https://doi.org/10.33963/KP.a2021.0040>
- [21] Higashi, H. Inaba, S., Ogimoto, A., Okura, T., Higaki, J., Okayama, H., Atherosclerotic renal artery stenosis mimicking fibromuscular dysplasia, *EJVES Extra* **2011**; 22, e44-e47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejvs.2011.07.007>.
- [22] Mota, R., Homeister, J.W., Willis, M.S., Bahnson, M., Atherosclerosis: Pathogenesis, Genetics, and Experimental Models, **2017** online 31st October. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470015902.a0005998.pub3>
- [23] Persu, A.; Canning, C.; Prejbisz, A.; Dobrowolski, P.; Amar, L.; Chrysochou, C.; Kadziela, J.; Litwin, M.; Twist, D.; Niepen, P.; Wuerzner, G.; Leeuw, P.; Azizi, M.; Januszewicz, M.; Januszewicz, A. Beyond Atherosclerosis and Fibromuscular dysplasia: Rare causes of Renovascular hypertension, *Hypertension.* **2021**;78:898-911. <https://doi.org/10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.121.17004>
- [24] Katelaris, P.; Hunt, R.; Bazzoli, F.; Cohen, H.; Fock, K.M.; Gemilyan, M.; Malfertheiner, P.; Megraud, F.; Piscocoy, A.; Quach, D.; Vakil, N.; Coelho, L.G.; LeMair, A. World Gastroenterology Organisation Global Guidelines Helicobacter Pylori. May **2021**. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MCG.0000000000001719>
- [25] Mohammed, N.S. The effects of dairy products on the therapeutic regimen of patients with Helicobacter Pylori infection in Aden, Yemen. *AJSRP*; **2018**; (4)2. <https://doi.org/10.26389/AJSRP.N110518>
- [26] Al-Ashwal, N.S. Diagnosis of Helicobacter Pylori: a guide to diagnosis of Helicobacter Pylori by clinical and ultrasonography approaches, *rabian Gulf House* **2020**. <https://aghpublishing.com/product/book-02-3112020>
- [27] Aramouni, K.; Assaf, R. K.; Azar, M.; Jabbour, K.; Shaito, A.; Sahebker, A.; Eid A.A.; Rizzo, M. & Eid, A.H. Infection with Helicobacter Pylori may predispose to atherosclerosis: role of inflammation and thickening of intima-media of carotide arteries. *Front. Pharmacol.* **2023**; 14:1285754. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2023.1285754>
- [28] Vilaplana-Carnerero, C.; Giner-Soriano, M.; Dominguez, A.; Morros, R.; Pericas, C.; Alamo-Junquera, D.; Toledo, D.; Gallego, C.; Redondo, A.; Grau, M. Atherosclerosis, Cardiovascular Disease, and COVID-19: A Narrative Review. *Biomedicines* **2023**, 11, 1206. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines11041206>